

Paranormal Interpretation Of The Episode Of Khizr Alayh Salaam

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Abstract: In this article, the story of one of the leading representatives of modern Uzbek prose, Isajon Sultan, titled "Hazrati Khizr Izidan" is analyzed, and attention is paid to the issue of the genesis of the image of Khizr alayhissalam, which is widespread in the folklore of Turkic peoples due to its longevity and usefulness. The continuous continuation of episodes about Khizr alayhissalam in modern Uzbek literature is shown by the examples of Togay Murad's stories "People walking on the moon" and Luqman Borikhan's "The Guard of the Stream or the Boy Who Khizr Saw". The religious-educational, social-psychological, artistic-aesthetic factors of the paranormal episodes that appeared in connection with this image were discussed.

Keywords — image, plot, detail, episode, paranormal episode, character, chronotope, motive, cult, animal spring, era, lick.

INTRODUCTION.

Uzbek folklore has its own rich heritage. Tales, epics, myths and legends, which have not lost their value and artistic significance over the centuries, have become part of our lives with their heroes. If we want to be like the hero of a fairy tale, myth or work, we want to meet another hero in life. One of the famous characters among the oral creativity, mythology and written literature of the Turkic peoples is the hero Khizr, who is remembered by the people as "the one who eases difficulties" and "the bringer of happiness". Everyone dreamed of meeting Khizr at least once in his life.

According to "Principles of Gestalt" [7:14], the image of Khizr is a sign of happiness. According to the beliefs of the Uzbek people, Khizr has no bone in his thumb, and the person who meets him should hold this finger and then ask for three wishes. Khizr, peace be upon him, responds to the needs of the needy in this way. because of such beliefs, he has become a symbol of cleanliness among the people. "He who is guided by Khizr will be happy forever" [6:10]. People who help when a person is in a difficult situation: "Aren't you Khizr?" - they ask.

This image has its own colorful features, and first of all, the essence of the image is determined by its vitality and wisdom. Among the people, he is depicted as an enlightened old man wearing a green or white robe. He wanders day and night without rest, without being seen by people. Scientist Shamirza Turdimov states: "Only those who have reached perfection among people can recognize Khizr and see him constantly" [pages 10:41-44]. When it is needed, it appears suddenly. People call him Hojai Khizr, Hazrat Khizr, Khizr Baba. It seems that there is some wisdom in Hazrat Navoi's saying, "Whoever you see, know Khizr, and every night you see, appreciate it." It is said that Khizr meets every person three times during his life and fulfills three wishes. But in most cases, many people do not know that they have met Khizr. It is possible to recognize that Khizr's thumb is boneless, as

mentioned above, only by one sign. Scientist Shamirza Turdimov stated: "The motif of asking Khizr for life, children, state, career is often found, or Khizr asks the person he meets to choose one of two conflicting goals." [Page 10:41-44] A person who has seen Khizr is respectfully called by such terms as "Khizr korgan", "Khizr dorigan". The above points about Khizr's personality have a vital basis.

In this article, we will focus on how Khizr's personality is reflected in mythology, folklore, and religious sources, and his artistic function as an image forming a paranormal episode in modern Uzbek stories.

So what is a paranormal episode? the question arises. What is its dictionary meaning?

The dictionary meaning of the word "paranormal" is normal, that is, something outside the usual limits, a situation, events, phenomena. "Paranormal episode" is unusual images associated with the third world used in works of art, disruption of traditional reality, events and processes occurring in the adjacent world. "Paranormal Episodes" include various paranormal events, a demon, a wrinkled giant, an alvasti, a blackbird, a black shadow, a devil, a devil, a snake-girl, a dog-man, Khizr and hokozos. In fact, all have their roots in religious, mythological and folklore sources. The above-mentioned figures are called demonological characters in folklore and mythology. In our research, we analyzed not only images, but also subjects and unusual events, and for this reason, we think it is appropriate to call it a paranormal episode.

In general, there are different interpretations and views of the image of Khizr in mythology, folklore, religious and written literature. In mythology, Khizr is a magical figure who performs sorcery and extraordinary miracles, in folklore sources as a person who suddenly appears in necessary and difficult situations, sometimes as a constant companion, and in

religious sources as a "righteous servant", a seer, as a storehouse, and in written literature it is embodied as a "fountain animal" - a permanent living person who has found the water of life.

Our scientists have different opinions about the image of Khizr, which is relatively ancient among mythological images. E. Bertels connects it to the gods associated with the world of ancient plants, [6:10] Bahadir Sarimsakov Khizr said that he was a priest of kinnats before the emergence of Islam and was worshiped by many people, as well as the etymology of his origin states that Zoroastrian beliefs are associated with [pp.1:193-194].

In the book "Uzbek Mythology and Arab Folklore", Mamatqul Jorayev and Sh. Shomusarov make the following points about Khizr: serves to clarify imagination and artistic interpretations.

1. Khizr is a legendary savior who patronizes people who have fallen into trouble;
2. Khizr is a wise man who does good to people with his clever advice;
3. Khizr is a legendary hero who gained eternal life because he found and drank the water of eternal life;
4. Khizr - an unusual person who opened the eyes of healing springs;
5. A symbol of goodness that appears out of nowhere in deserts and deserts and helps people in a difficult situation;
6. Khizr is a symbol of fertility that bestows a bountiful harvest and blessings on the farmer's field;
7. One of the noble or beloved saints who always support the good people. [4] As for the roots of the image of Khizr, the authors make the following conclusions: "In the emergence of the image of Khizr, the beliefs of our grandfathers who lived in ancient times, related to the worship of ancestors, played an important role." [4] Also, scientists emphasize that the personality of Khizr is considered a noble patron directly connected with the water cult.

Azerbaijani scientist M. Seyidov, who studied the folklore and ethnography of Turkic peoples, attaches special importance to the image of Khizr in his research "Foundations of the Mythic Thought of Azerbaijan". The scientist went deeper into the origin of Khizr's personality and found the word Khizr from two parts: "xyz" - meaning "heat", "warm", and "yr" meaning "person", "respectable", "holy god". explains that [Seyidov, 1983, 107].

Folklorist scientist Shamirza Turdimov connects Khizr's personality with the image of "eran" who always supports and patronizes the main characters in "Goroghli" epics, and as a basis, Goro believes that the person who sees Khizr will have a long life. It is emphasized in the example of 'g'li.

Another scholar, Najmiddin Kamilov, wrote in the book "Tasavvuf": "Khoja Khizr drank the water of life - the water of eternal life, he is aware of all events, all situations, all experiences; he knows the nature and laws of things in advance, God has gifted him with his knowledge" [5:39] are also noteworthy.

In English-language sources, Khizr's personality is associated with the Hidrellez holiday. Hidrellez is one of the seasonal holidays of the entire Turkic world. The Day of Hidrellez known as Ruz-i Khizr (Day of Khizr) is celebrated as the day when Prophets Khizr and Ilyas met on earth. Khizr and Ilyas have since been pronounced Hidrellez. Elijah, peace be upon him, is one of the prophets of Banu Israel. He was a descendant of Harun, peace be upon him, and was called Ilyas ibn Yasin. Ilyas alayhissalam in the land of Sham, more precisely in the city of Balabakka in the current state of Lebanon while living there, he was sent to a people who worshiped Ba'al, and died there. Hydralles Day falls on May 6 in the Gregorian calendar. There are different theories about the origin of Khizr and Hidrellez. Some of these indicate that Hidrellez belongs to the Mesopotamian and Anatolian cultures, while others refer to the pre-Islamic Central Asian Turkic culture and beliefs. However, the celebration of Hidrellez and the beliefs surrounding Khizr cannot be attributed to a single culture. Since ancient times, in Mesopotamia, Anatolia, Iran, Greece, and in fact in all the countries of the eastern Mediterranean, different ceremonies for different gods have been held with the arrival of spring or summer.

The main part. Above, we have considered the mythology, folklore sources and life foundations of the roots of Khizr's personality as examples of various considerations. In our opinion, analysis of our research according to Islamic principles will make Khizr's personality more clear to us, and also the Islamic foundation is important in the interpretation of Khizr's image in modern literature.

The holy book of Islam "Qur'an" does not mention the word Khizr, but refers to Khizr through the term "righteous servant". From verse 60 to verse 82 of Surah "Kahf" of the Holy Qur'an, the exemplary journey of Moses and Khizr is presented. "Remember when Moses said to his young man, 'Even if I spend years, I will walk until I reach the place where the two seas meet.' (When Moses was giving a sermon one day among Bani Israel, he was asked which of the people was the most knowledgeable. He said: "I." God rewarded him for attributing knowledge to himself. He said to Moses: "The two seas joined there is a servant of mine. He said: "O my Lord, how shall I find him?" After that, they prepared for the journey and told their servants the decision that came in the above verse. He decided to go to the place where the two seas are gathered." [12: 500] -pages 501]

Burhanuddin Rabguzi in his work "Qissasi Rabg'uziy" quotes the following points: "The meaning of Khizr is green. When he killed Khizr with a stone, the land turned green. Some

people said that Khizr was angry. Some people say that it is not a lick, he was righteous, muslih erdi. It's fun. He grew up in Bani Israel. Mangu survived by drinking suyin, but Ilyas mursal is still standing" [Rabguzi 1990, 28].

In the works of Alisher Navoi, thoughts about Khizr's prophethood and patronage of the savior can be observed. Navoi, of course, relied on the Islamic foundations of the legends related to Khizr and reflected them in this way in his works.

In the monograph "Chronotope poetics in Alisher Navoi's "Khamsa"" written by the literary scholar Uzoq Djurakulov, the following thoughts about Khizr's personality are of particular importance. "The introduction of the image of Khizr into the folklore and written literature of the peoples of the world is more related to myths and folklore. This image, sometimes changing its name, sometimes its artistic function, sometimes its position, has been passing from century to century. But there are three characteristics that he has preserved over time, which will never change. Even these three features ensure the viability of the image in the literary process. These are the characteristics of extraordinary knowledge, eternal life and globalism in the image of Khizr. [11:250-b]

How is Khizr alayhissalam, mentioned in the Holy Qur'an, hadith, folklore and mythological sources, alive in oral and written literature for centuries, embodied in modern Uzbek prose, especially in short stories? For what poetic purposes did the writers use the image of Khizr and the events related to him, and what is his artistic function in modern Uzbek short stories? The main issues of our research are such questions.

We know that in the works created in recent years, the deepening of the philosophical content is observed, and great attention is paid to realism and religious-mythological and folklore sources in expressing the philosophical foundations of the artistic work. One of the works in this spirit is Isajon Sultan's short story "Hazrat Khizr Izidan". In this story, Khizr alayhissalam is taken as the main motif, and the work relies on Islamic sources about its origin. In particular, from the 60th to the 82nd verse of the Holy Qur'an Surah "Kahf", the exemplary journey of Hazrat Khizr and Musa a.s. is taken as the main motive in this story. "In the short story, the writer unites the past-present-future events in one loop based on the retrospective subject". [9: 124- b]

The compositional structure of the work consists of seven parts, and each part covers several events in the form of a forming story. It is presented in a formative way, it reminds us of the fourth epic of "Khamsa" "Sabayi Sayor". "The work allows us to observe that the work was created in harmony with the most modern sciences related to the world of the unseen, from the oldest myths and legends, narratives and stories found in the Uzbek and world nations related to Hazrat Khizr" - says Kurdosh Kahramanov. [Pages 2:64-65] In the first part, "Incident in Kyzilkum", "Dashtu Tuz", "Incident between the Mountains", "Incident in Wheat Field", "The Story of Yunus Khalfa" are presented in the form of small stories. , at the center

of all of them is Khizr, peace be upon him, and his survival and needs. It is in this part that the mystery of the world, from the smallest particles to the animals and plants, and the fact that God does not leave any of his creatures in a difficult situation, is reflected as a paranormal episode of a baby gazelle suffering from dehydration and an old man in green who came to his aid.

In the second part, "The Story of the Thief of Abar", "The Story of the Nanny", "The Story of the Learned Man and the Madman" and saints with various blessings (Invisible father, Snake father, So'galli father, Lion father, a saint without arms and his basket weaving, a saint who can see without eyes, a saint who walks on the surface of water) will be depicted. Especially the instructive thoughts from the tongue of the saint who can walk on the surface of the water as if he were walking on the ground invite each of us to observe. "Don't be fooled by the blue sky above you and the hard ground below you. You are all walking on water. Aren't you afraid that whatever he wants will be torn apart and drowned in the abyss?" [3:170]

In the third part, the chronotope of the work is connected to today. During a lecture on "Folk narratives and modern science" by a scientist from Egypt to the students of the university, the personality of Donish Domla is introduced to the student. He completely denies the good deeds and existence of Hazrat Khizr, emphasizes that today man himself has become Khizr, and shows that he is an "intelligent person" in quotation marks. Through teacher Donish, the author describes the generalized image of people who do not follow their knowledge, turn towards blasphemy, look down on national values and traditions, and consider material benefit as the basis of life.

Also, in this part, the meeting of Khizr alayhissalam and Musa a.s. and their journey is described in the language of an Egyptian scholar in "The incident on the shore of the Red Sea". The ability of Khizr to foresee unpleasant events and the fact that in any case one should not judge the situation based on the surface can be seen in the example of Musa a.s. Already, a ship was pierced so that the property of the poor could be kept, a child who was predicted to be an infidel when he grew up was killed so that his believing parents would not be harmed, and a broken wall was repaired so that the treasure belonging to an orphan could be hidden. At the heart of all the events, Khizr's supernatural strength, science and lore, the qualities of a "spooky animal" and the interpretation as a paranormal episode increase the artistic power of the work.

In the later parts of the work, emphasis is placed on the issue of "silai rahm", which is one of the sacred values in Islam. Relationships between parents, brothers, sisters, intimate and romantic feelings are depicted in the dreams of brothers. It is in these parts that the main idea of the work becomes more deeply understood. Turning to the personality of Hazrat Khizr, the author tries to reveal all his religious-mythological, folklore and life foundations, his thoughts and philosophical views about the meaning of life through the episode of Khizr. He laments that his parents, who are the umbrella at the

beginning of man's life from birth to adulthood, are at the level of Khizr, but the human race dreams of meeting Khizr for a lifetime. Indeed, knowing in advance the trials that will happen to us, why not honor our parents and loved ones who are always there for us, who help us at every moment, and who are close to us? Why does a person envy the fate of others without appreciating everything in himself? Is this what they say, "the water that flows in front of you has no value"?

Summarizing our thoughts, the reference to religious sources in this work is reminiscent of the traditional style in our classical literature. The author describes his philosophical views with the help of Khizr's personality in a mixed state with today's artistic colors. In general, among our people, Khizr alayhissalam is a paranormal episode that is always imagined as a benevolent patron. It is mythological related to the eternal life of Khizr, that is, he will never die views are also reflected in the concept of "Khizr's life". In the work, the author writes in "Ena's Story" from the Ena language, "Did God create him in vain?" Small worms and insects have a job, shouldn't it be Khizr's?" [Page 3:178] emphasizes the vitality of Khizr.

In Uncle Murad's short story "People Walking in the Moon", Khizr alayhissalam was included as a paranormal episode based on the motive of asking for a child. Khizr a.s. appears twice to the hero of the play, the Leopard, and he asks Khizr to give him a child. Khizr a.s. answers that you will still have many children. In a symbolic sense, the children of Koplombek and Oymomo are considered representatives of the next generation.

The image of Khizr is also found in Luqman Borikhan's short story "The Guard of the Pond or the Boy Who Khizr Saw". In this story, the quality of Khizr's character, which is widespread among the people, is expressed in the life of the hero of the work with sincere and light laughter.

Conclusion. In short, "paranormal episodes" have been an integral part of literature since time immemorial. Be it mythological, religious, folklore, or modern literature, these episodes fulfill their artistic function as a symbol, a tool that shows the ideas and goals of the creators in their works. In the above-mentioned story of Isajan Sultan "In the Footsteps of Hazrat Khizr", the prophetic qualities of Khizr, peace be upon him, are emphasized. The writer was aware of mythological, folklore and oral narratives about Khizr a.s. In our opinion, Khizr alayhissalam appeared as a "paranormal episode" in Qissa, and the events related to him served as the main motive of the work.

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